

Asian Political Development and Cooperation in Nuclear Non Proliferation

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Abstract

Over the past two decades, the political development of nuclear states in South Asia derailed the nuclear nonproliferation process, at the current stage, five countries in Asia possess the nuclear arsenal, while in past twenty years, no major war has been noticed but relying on the state relations of Asian countries with their neighbours erected a question whether nuclear nonproliferation and disarmament are feasible in Asia. The historical enmity among these nations remained the driving force resulted in numerous wars and minor scale conflicts, recorded between India and Pakistan, Chinese involvement in the Korean peninsula war, conflict with India in Siachen, Ladakh, and northeastern region, indicating that the probability of war between these Asian nations is exceptionally high concerning the prospects of peace on the Asian continent. The strategic alliances of western nations with Asian countries, especially during conflict and war times, is considered the reason for the proliferation of nuclear weapons in Asia. The treaty on the nonproliferation of nuclear weapons aiming to prevent the spread of atomic weapons failed to address the concerns of Asian countries, which resulted three nuclear power opposition in Asia alone. The failure of bilateral dialogues among the nuclear states prolonged the threat of major nuclear conflict in Asia seems not to be resolved with traditional western approaches of gunboat diplomacy and brinkmanship, especially in the case of India and Pakistan. This paper evaluates the current status of nuclear nonproliferation development in Asia while considering the historical conflict to comprehend realistic triggers points that could escalate the nuclear war, taking into accounts both the state actors and non-state actors influence in the development of national security threats, also laying down comprehensive approaches to tackle the current nuclear posture of the nuclear states simultaneously emphasizing plans on the avoidance of such trigger by evaluating current Asian political development regarding nuclear diplomacy through an empirical process analyzing all possible strategies furthering nuclear nonproliferation in Asia.

Keywords: Nuclear Disarmament, Defense Security, Foreign Relations, Asian Geopolitics, Nonproliferation

Introduction

The security dilemma in matters of arms control exists since the emergence of civilizations where the state must decide whether they should proliferate armaments to tackle the anarchy of the international order or remain unarm letting the security vulnerable against the potential adversary. Thucydides addressed this dilemma in his notable work "The Peloponnese war" where Sparta and Athens two bipolar state's fear and uncertainty among each other became the driving force leading to war. Taking the last two decades of Asian geopolitical development into accounts, forecasting unpredictable Asia's future in terms of nuclear nonproliferation and peaceful coexistence, the Russian annexation of Crimea in 2014, rift over the disputed territory in the Himalayan region between three nuclear powers, the China assertion its sovereignty over the South China sea, the surge of United States bases near China, Taliban control in Afghanistan adding more to it, the undeclared new nuclear arms race in Asia between India and Pakistan frightening the government officials across the globe. Asia is in a great mess regarding neighborhood relations what contributes more to this mess is the risk of war escalation threatens the use of nuclear warheads. The rationale behind obtaining a nuclear weapon is deterrence which is the prevention of the status quo by threatening unacceptable costs to an opponent if they conduct an unacceptable behavior includes Deterrence by punishment punishing the adversary by inflicting unbearable destruction, another one is denial deterrence by denial means persuading the adversary not to attack by convincing him that any conduct which threatened the country might meet a quick response by nuclear retaliation, this policy could be seen in North Korea and Pakistan nuclear postures. There are three requirements for deterrence first is Capability if the country does not possess adequate counter weapons, it might not be considered as a threat by the adversary in a larger sense, the second Credibility that the country will use the

weapon if the adversary crosses the line and last is Communication if there is lack of communication about those lines could trigger the nuclear war even if unintentionally crossed. The absence of dialogues might lead to unnecessary escalation to war especially in the case of India and Pakistan where the ideological submission might inhibit the rationality behind the act. Observing the political development regarding deterrence gives us a broad picture of the possible escalation of nuclear conflict.

PART I Nuclear Postures and Politics

When the German scientists discovered nuclear fission energy Albert Einsteinⁱ wrote a letter to President Roosevelt warning that Germany might build an atomic bomb, which led to the establishment of the Manhattan project consisting US and Britain aiming to develop a nuclear bomb before the Nazis. The Germans surrendered on 7 May 1945, regardless of that, on 16 July 1945, the first-ever nuclear test was conducted, known as the Trinity test, this was the earliest example of proliferation by fear which played a critical role in the proliferation of weapons in the coming decades. Humankind has exercised the instrument of its destruction, a huge mushroom cloud formed over Hiroshima, and three days later on Nagasaki, which led the mass wave of uncertainty in the Soviet Union regarding their existence.

1.1 Russia- To offset the US policy of "monopolize then disarm"ⁱⁱ under the Baruch Plan, the Soviet Union rejected it due to the psychological impact of nuclear weapons and the suspicion of the western nations. Fear and uncertainty played a decisive role in the development of the Russian nuclear program where Klaus Fuchsⁱⁱⁱ, a German theoretical physicist during his work in the Manhattan project, defected and supplied critical information to the Soviets, which significantly contributed to the advancement of the Soviet Nuclear Program resulted in tremendous success when first nuclear bomb tested in 1949. This earlier setback to limit proliferation soon attracted the Britishers, who conducted the nuclear weapons test in 1952, followed by the French nuclear test in 1960. The Soviet Union safeguarding the spread of communism in Asia played a greater role in The Chinese civil war, Korean peninsula war, Turkish crisis 1953, Vietnam war, and the infamous Cuban Missile Crisis which brought the world to the brink of nuclear war, contributing more to it in 1962, the Soviet Union tested the world's largest nuclear weapon ever, the "TZAR bomb," which had the yield of 50 megatons equivalent to 500 Hiroshima bombs initially planned 100 megatons. Soviets were not stopped here and further the assistance to the Chinese nuclear program who later conducted a successful nuclear test in 1964. As these negative development advanced both internationally and in nuclear physics led to the realization of atomic threat, which resulted in the Antarctic treaty in 1957, The Partial test ban Treaty in 1963, the Anti-ballistic missile treaty 1972, Strategic Arms Limitation Talks 1972 & 1979 restricted certain weapons and limited the nuclear arsenal, Intermediate-Range Nuclear Force treaty 1987 further the development of nonproliferation aiming at dismantling the missiles range under 5500 km. What the Russians reflected through these agreements is the willingness to work and further, the nonproliferation commitment of Article VI of the Nonproliferation treaty (obligation to reduce the arsenal and disarm), safeguarding civilization not only from the nuclear threats simultaneously redefined nuclear weapons status. The US leadership before the 1970s was willing to exercise nuclear weapons in the Korean War^{iv}, Vietnam war^v, and on China in 1958^{vi} in response to China's shelling in the Taiwan strait, which largely shifted because of these treaties. The Strategic Arms Reduction Treaty 1 in 1991 barred the signatory from deploying more than 6000 nuclear warheads and 1600 ICBM, which expired in 2009, despite the success of START 1 the START 2 aiming at de-MIRVing means multiple independently targetable re-entry vehicles not to be used on ICBM ratified by the USA in 1996 and by Russian in 2000 but later the Russians withdrawal in 2002, in response to US withdrawal from ABM Treaty citing constraints on missiles questioned the US commitment. To promote arms control a new treaty was signed known as Strategic Offensive Reductions Treaty 2002, again reducing the armament to between 1,700–2,200 by 2012, and the recent New START treaty 2010 has been conducted, putting limitations of 700 on deployed missiles and bombers 800 on deployed launchers and 1550 on deployed nuclear warheads. These developments took a hit when Russians annexed Crimea and welcomed sanctions. Recently in response to The US withdrawal from the INF Treaty in 2019, Russian concluded their exit from the open skies treaty hitting new lows between the West and Russian relationship.

1.2 The Peoples Republic of China- After the first Taiwan Strait crisis, Mao decided to build the nuclear weapons program in 1953-54 through initial assistance from the Soviet Union before the split of 1959, the PRC successfully conducted the nuclear test in 1964 and shortly after the test China stated "*not to be the first to use nuclear weapons at any time or under any circumstance*"^{vii} indicated the no first use policy but when first hydrogen bomb test occurred in 1967 of 3.3 megatons which unleashed the wave of fear among Indian officials who witnessed the defeat just five years ago. The biggest yield bomb was four megatons tested in 1976 and simultaneously concluded a total of 45 nuclear tests until 1996 when China signed the Comprehensive Test Ban

Treaty. The China defense white paper^{viii}, repeated its nuclear policy commitment of a no-first-use pledge. Concerning nuclear cooperation, China is part of the NPT and stated that PRC abides by its treaty obligations, however in practice, its advance towards modernization^{ix} of nuclear arsenal and covertly supported the non-NPT state proliferation breaching the NPT obligations in the case of Pakistan and North Korea.

1.3 India- The Indians started the civilian nuclear program by building its first research reactor in 1956 aimed at the generation of energy reaffirmed by Former prime minister Jawaharlal Nehru stating: "India will not misuse the nuclear energy^x" and will remain a non-nuclear weapon state, also made the first proposal calling for an agreement to ban nuclear weapons tests in 1954, alas, this call was not heeded and also rejected Kennedy's offer^{xi} of nuclear detonation in 1962, strongly stood on the oath. But within few years India found itself in a war with China in 1962 in the Himalayan region ended in great defeat reshaping the foreign policy posture, the debate of a deterrence mainstreamed after successful nuclear test conducted by PRC in 1964, the continuous wars with Pakistan, which the United States of America supported, exposed the threat to Indian sovereignty resulted in 1974 India first Peaceful nuclear test which soon attracted sanctions isolating the Indian atomic program for next 15 years. The Zia threat of militarizing its nuclear technology and exercise for Kashmir liberation forced India to bring the nuclear program out of dormancy in 1989. Despite the December 1995 failure, India's successfully concluded five fission devices test at Pokhran Rajasthan in May 1998. The press notes of 04, January 2003 considered as unofficial nuclear doctrine emphasizing "no first use by prioritizing building and maintaining a credible minimum deterrent however, "if India is under attack or any chemical and biological weapon used against the Indian army anywhere, the complication will be nuclear retaliation"^{xii}.

1.4 Pakistan- In 1965, the former Pakistani prime minister Zulfikar Bhutto stated that "Pakistan will eat grass but will obtain the nuclear weapon^{xiii}" and began the military nuclear program in January 1972, after the humiliating loss of East Pakistan. This rationale is reflected in the nuclear posture of Pakistan, giving the authority to use the nuclear weapon first, empowering the brigadier to use tactical nuclear weapons in response to invasion. Abdul Qadeer Khan played a massive role in development of the Pakistani nuclear program where he illegally supplied^{xiv} centrifuge designs, a list of about 100 suppliers of centrifuge parts and materials from the URENCO uranium-enrichment facility in the Netherlands and sent to Pakistan. The Dutch Intelligence reported this development to the United States, but the USA turned a blind eye^{xv} to this development because of its alliance with Pakistan against the Soviet Union during the Russo-Afghan war in 1979. Thomas Reed, former US Secretary of the Air Force, revealed^{xvi} the PRC transfer nuclear technology to Pakistan since 1982. The nuclearization of Pakistan was a slow march, but by Chinese assistance^{xvii} of CHIC-4 design, 50kg highly enriched uranium in 1983 contributed immensely to the development. By 1986 US was convinced Pakistan is nuclear-capable but not considered any containment action. In March 1987, Zia claimed Pakistan has the capability to make a bomb which analyst believe by 1987 Pakistan covertly developed the bomb but tested it two weeks after the Indian Pokhran Test of 1998.

1.5 North Korea – According to reports, North Korea was in talks with the Soviets and Pakistan in 1980s however in 1994, when Pakistan offers North Korea a route to nuclear weapons using HEU, against payment waive off for the No-Dong missile^{xviii} the plan came in existence. The same year, North Korea intended to withdraw from the NPT they were part of since 1985, which the United States avoided, and signed the Agreed Framework with North Korea freezing the Pyongyang plutonium weapons program in exchange of aid. The deal collapsed in 2002, and North Korea officially withdraw from NPT. To counter any aggressive measure United States initiated six-party talks nonetheless North Korea tested the nuclear weapon in 2006, breaking 1992 treaty of denuclearization of the Korean peninsula^{xix}, since then, several atomic weapons have been tested by North Korea, in July 2017, it tested its first ICBMs, and in September 2017, it conducted a test claimed was a thermonuclear weapon. However, North Koreans later came to negotiate disarmament in 2018-2019.

Total Stockpiles Table

Declassified Nuclear material/Devices Information

Head	ICBM	Range Km	Largest Yield	Nuclear Submarines SSBN SSN SSK	Nuclear Devices	HEU PU-239	Nuclear Reactor
Russia	527	18,000	50 MT	11 17 21	6255	629 T 128 T	38
China	90	15,000	4 MT	4 6 50	350	14 T 2.9 T	50
North Korea	2	10,000	260 KT	2 0 0	40	NA	0
Pakistan	0	2750	45 KT	0 0 5	165	3.7 T 0.37 T	6
India	5	5500	45 KT	1 1 12	156	4.4 T 0.60 T	23

Data Source: Nuclear Threat Initiative^{xx}, SIPRI Report 2021^{xxi}, The Statista^{xxii}

N/A: No Information, **T:** Ton, **MT:** Megaton, **KT:** Kiloton

The declassified data is critical for analyzing a nation's credibility and capacity, which could be a great indicator of the future proliferation potential one nation possesses. Till now we have analyzed the nuclear posture and declassified data, enabling us to comprehend it with political development, especially regarding the state actors who play a significant role in nonproliferation simultaneously escalation of the war.

PART II The Modern Machiavellian International Order

2.1 The Russian Bear

The Northern Atlantic Treaty Organization is taking active measures in Ukraine by conducting Cossack mace 2021 joint^{xxiii} military drills in Ukraine with Britain involving NATO member troops. The United States unweaving support for Ukraine^{xxiv}, deployment of arms in eastern Europe, and conducting drills in near Russian federation sending a message of encirclement of Russia. Eastern Ukraine is the epicenter of conventional war, and the unstable EU behavior regarding Russians witnessed in Feb 2021^{xxv}, forcing the Kremlin to strengthen ties with China. This development benefiting Russia in terms of expanding its economic relations with China regarding Military and workforce while China gains a considerable advantage in UNSC over Taiwan issue simultaneously got the opportunity to modernize their weapons with the assistance of Russia, which could be seen in joint development of nuclear reactor in Taiwan Nuclear Power Plant and the Xudapu NPP in China. The analyst Alexander Gabuev^{xxvi} believed the Sino-Russo alliance is based upon a condominium where Russia provides security by challenging the West simultaneously China sought development and stated that any alternative to friendship with China would be a disaster for Russia.

2.2 The Eastern Crimea

China's foreign policy considers Taiwan as their integral part, and any support or sympathizing with separatist forces is considered the breach of Anti-secession law, which will force China to reunify Taiwan by a force whose attempts witnessed during 1954, 1958, and 1996 where PRC dropped missiles near the shores of Taiwan as a warning. China will never relinquish her claim over Taiwan, which could be seen in the Chinese nuclear policy of NFP, which has one exception, "Japanese Exception Theory,^{xxvii}" highly accepted among the top Chinese officials where any attempt to obstruct Taiwan liberation by the Japanese will be welcome with a nuclear strike as a countering measure. The Japanese security legislation 2015 allows Japan to take collective self-defense^{xxviii} to defend the US in wartime and recent discussion to deploying missiles near Taiwan assumed as pre-war development by PRC. This suspicion became strong when 2021 Japan annual defense white paper^{xxix} stated that stabilizing the situation surrounding Taiwan is essential for Japan's security and the stability of the international community. The Taiwan relation acts are ambiguous in nature, does not confirm whether the US is obligated to protect Taiwan or will leave the matters up to circumstances. Will Taiwan reunification lead to war? the probability is too low because of the Crimean model, which the world witnessed, exposing the West's vulnerability against a potential adversary, the USA's reliance on PRC for north Korean disarmament^{xxx} despite the trade war reaffirm this possibility.

2.3 Russo Pak Alliance

Russia under Putin since 2011 shifted its posture where first, they condemned^{xxxi} the NATO strike on Pakistan, later bid for Pakistan to join SCO^{xxxii}, which followed by military Games and exercise in 2015 and "Friendship 2016" despite India unsuccessful request to Russia for calling off. In 2021 Russian sold Mi-35 helicopters to Pakistan, however, maintaining relations on both sides, Russia condemned Pakistan during 2020 at SCO and further the arms sales with India nonetheless, India is no longer a strategic^{xxxiii} partner for the Kremlin because of India leaning towards the west in the form of QUAD.

2.4 The Indo-Western Dilemma

Quadrilateral Security Dialogue strengthened by the Former President Trump to limit the Chinese aggression in the Pacific Sea, discomfited^{xxxiv} the Kremlin stating it will imbalance the regional power, peace and stability in the region might face the consequences which could be seen as Russia dropped warning bombs^{xxxv} near the British fleets who allegedly came too close to Russia in the black sea, China threatened a similar warning to the UK fleet near the south China sea. Russia-India-China initiatives favored by Moscow to advance the security and resolve diplomatic issues bilaterally however, India looks upon the West as an ally to contain China, ignoring that China's containment threatens Russian dominance in Asia and eastern Europe simultaneously, impacting India's position as a strategic partner for the Kremlin. From the Chinese perspective, the PRC has not yet deployed their strategical nuclear weapons on the Western Command to avoid any

intimidation posture from China concerning India, that China is preparing for a nuclear strike on the Indian territory. The PRC^{xxxvi} does not consider Indian nuclear arsenals a threat because the superiority of Chinese biggest nuclear yield of four megatons equivalent to 80-100 Indian largest nuclear weapon combined India ever tested. From the Indian perspective, China modernization of atomic weapons is threatening because when a country pursues modernization of their nuclear arsenal and reduces the diameter and the size of their weapons, it became a great indicator that the government is eager to make the nuclear weapon "usable." Furthermore, making it useable is to use it conventionally or strategically, when necessary, which is a matter of serious concern.

2.5 The Pakistani Question

The famous international relation theorist Kenneth Waltz stated in the 1980s^{xxxvii} that the proliferation of nuclear weapons brings stability in foreign relations due to the inevitability of mutually assured destruction nonetheless, democratic and nuclear peace theory proved incorrect in the south Asian context, it does prevent a large-scale conventional conflict but allows the aggressor state to conduct small scale proxy war under nuclear shadow and threaten the target state if they retaliate against their aggression. Since Pakistan nuclearization, seven major attacks had been executed 1989 Kashmir, 1993 Mumbai, 1999 Kargil war, The Parliament attack, Mumbai 26/11, Pathankot 2016, the 2019 Pulwama attack eventually led to a surgical strike on Pakistan, while in response Prime minister of Pakistan threatened about a possible nuclear war in the future on Kashmir.^{xxxviii}

2.6 Cost of Under deterrence for India

The majority of Indian nuclear weapons are in civilian custody^{xxxix}, such as DAE, DRDO, SFC and India refrain exercise them however, any conventional or non-conventional act that brings enormous damage to Indians through a terrorist attack might arouse three possibilities from the Indian standpoint first possibility is that it will trigger the nuclear weapons as retaliation against Pakistan. The second realistic development could be that if the Indian government refrained from retaliating due to global pressure, the military will overthrow the Indian government, jeopardizing Pakistan existence. The last is the most conventional which India Pakistan witnessed is the surgical strike took place in 2019. It is an escape from conventional responsibility and exercise as a warning tool. If Pakistan kept increasing the aggression, then India might retaliate. Pakistan know this very well to avoid this the bar of nuclear use is reduced by Pakistan and can exercise even if the Indian army conducted a cross border punitive strike to a terrorist attack safeguarding the militants who could be considered an asset for Pakistan.

2.7 The False Alarm

It was reported numerous times in 1979-1980^{xl} when computers intercepted 1400-2,200 Soviet missiles launched against the United States similar development reported in 1983^{xli}, the system signaled that the United States had launched a rocket toward the Soviet Union, again the officer in the Soviet camps was not convinced and retaliation was avoided, however, in India Pakistan context is relatively high wherein Pakistan misinterpretation of the signals due to system vulnerability that might trigger the nuclear war because of the short time of five to six minutes to react one such instance was during the Feb 2019 crisis Indian Prime minister alerted the Indian nuclear Submarine^{xlii}, raising the tension of the possible conflict however, the Pakistan navy failed to intercept the message, a possible war avoided.

2.8 The Non-State Actor

In 2001, the news broke out after 9/11 that in 1999^{xliii} Pakistan military officials talked with Taliban leaders about the placement of nuclear weapons in Afghanistan^{xliv} in order to maximize the deterrence, this reveals the terror nexus that Pakistan in time of war could supply the nuclear weapons to non-state actors in order to neutralize India without directly taking the blame reaffirmed in July 2019, Prime Minister Imran Khan admitted^{xlv} that Pakistan accommodating 40 terror militia groups consisting of 30,000-40,000 terrorists conducting operations from their soil is a more significant threat for global peace. According to several reports, it was confirmed that ISI is assisting the Lashkar-e-Taiba^{xlvi} and operating the terrorist attacks in the Himalayan region from Pakistan, these terror groups activity is aligned with the long term greater national interest of uniting the Kashmir region with Pakistan it holds the legitimacy and popular support by the Pakistan government both ideologically and financially. The question may raise could a terror outfit develop nuclear weapons, in 1976, Princeton university student John Aristotle Philips^{xlvii} developed the nuclear weapons design simply by gathering the information from books, later the FBI confiscated it. In 1995 Tokyo, when a religious group called Aum Shinrikyo^{xlviii} initiated a chemical attack on the Tokyo subway, reports suggested that the initial plan was a nuclear detonation but dropped plans due to time constraints this depicts that developing a WMD is not that hard if required materials are available. Regarding non-actor states, the primary concern is the private contractors and

maritime security vulnerability, today millions of containers were moving across the globe, as this number surge, the probability of transferring fissile material by cargo increases, such as an improvised nuclear device could transfer, which was witnessed in 2010 when Al Qaeda sent the explosive by storing it in a printer shipped from Yemen^{xlix}, similar development intercepted in 2003 when the British and the US intercepted German cargo coming from Dubai to Libya containing centrifuge parts list based upon the Pakistani design, later it revealed that AQ Khan between 1997-2000 supplied P-1 designs nuclear technology ordered by North Korea, simultaneously assisted Iran and Libya with P-1 and P-2 designs in 1999, confirmed by Pakistani President Pervez Musharraf his memoir^l published in 2006.

PART III Remedies

Numerous studies during the cold war shown that the primary rationale behind the proliferation is to inflict enormous destruction to the adversary, aimed at slow down the recovery so that an imbalance in the international hemisphere of power both in terms of economics and political influence could be developed leaning in favor of the country who initiated that attack which in today spectrum cannot be possible due to globalization and interconnection between countries.

3.1 De-escalations: The territorial claim relinquishment is vital for Russia Ukraine peace resolution, whose prerequisites are the NATO forces demilitarization in Eastern Europe. A similar development in Sino-Indo relations vital by reevaluating the Johnson line and McMahon line, but fundamental priority must be acknowledgment of POK as part of India by the PRC. Peace was offered to Pakistan numerous times by Indians, alas continuous treaty violations and proxy wars will force India to retrospect and refrain from initiating talks.

3.2 The US The Torch Bearer: The United States unilaterally must set an example for the world by reducing the nuclear weapon to that extent where no second-strike capacity remains alive, suspending one aspect of the deterrence by punishment. The adoption of no first use policy by the USA might advance the goal of nonproliferation, simultaneously restrict the president power to initiate a nuclear strike.

3.3 International Anti-Terror Regime: Resolution 1373 (2001)^{li} reaffirming the emergence to combat by all means, in accordance with the Charter of the United Nations, threats to international peace and security caused by terrorist acts, without an all-out multilateral approach against terror funder and aiding nations, peace cannot be restored. It must be a significant concern for the West to take a multilateral approach towards ending terrorism regardless of the political effects either by sanctions and if requires Iraqi model must be exercised against terror-sponsoring states.

3.4 No Sanctions Diplomacy: The 2018-19 Disarmament showed great response where North Korea dismantled one rocket site^{lii} but rebuild when talks with the USA deteriorated. In the upcoming decades, North Korea might escalate the war against South Korea to protect the economy in the worst-case scenario, a possible tradeoff with sophisticated terrorist outfits might take place. Ending the sanctions that restrict any possibility of exchanging nuclear information for monetary benefits is vital and will encourage the adoption of universal norms.

3.5 Regional Nuclear Cooperation Treaties: The Soviet- US experience's discussed earlier concluded that nonproliferation is possible but requires a bilateral approach, the existing nonproliferation treaty will never be going to achieve the task in Asia unless the Governments adapt to the "Regional Nuclear Cooperation Treaties", all the international regimes treaties are erected mainly by the assumption of a particular commitment and few of them are legally bound. This "RNCT" not only bind the partners but will progress the aim of NPT. The Chinese and Indian officials are more likely to deescalate the tensions seen by annual Dialogues and hint that such initiatives might enable Asian countries to build back better world by promoting normalcy and transparency.

Conclusion

The possibility of nuclear disarmament in Asia is low due to several historical and geopolitical reasons nonetheless, the existence of the disarmament probability lies on the shoulders of Asian regional powers and western leaders where through a fusion of multilateral approaches and "lead by example", might prevent the proliferation of armaments across the globe which also fulfil the obligation of NPT treaty 1968 Article VI, simultaneously build trust among the traditional western sceptic Asian leaders, ensuring long term cooperation alongside the sustainability of the global peace. The multilateral approach among two countries inhibits the western officials from undertaking the perspective of Asian countries and their concerns. The proliferation of

nuclear weapons is the breed of fear and uncertainties erected from numerous reasons such as unstable western relations, security concerns and so on as the solutions laid out, it will take away the western skepticism, the emphasis upon RNCT, which can be legally binding far superior to the commitment assurance treaties. Diplomatic sanctions also hinder the opportunity of cooperation which must not exist in the era of globalization. The weapons of destruction are not the instruments of progression but the annihilation of the whole human race we must prioritize the end of proliferation, or we would not be alive to end once it is exercised.

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Reference

ⁱ “Einstein's Letter to President Roosevelt - 1939.” Einstein's Letter to President Roosevelt - 1939 | Historical Documents. Accessed August 4, 2021. <https://atomicarchive.com/resources/documents/beginnings/einstein.html>.

ⁱⁱ Staff, History. “The United States Presents the Baruch Plan.” History.com. A&E Television Networks, November 13, 2009. <https://www.history.com/this-day-in-history/the-united-states-presents-the-baruch-plan>.

ⁱⁱⁱ Staff, Atomic Heritage. “Klaus Fuchs.” Atomic Heritage Foundation, December 29, 1911. <https://www.atomicheritage.org/profile/klaus-fuchs>.

^{iv} Gwertzman, Bernard. “US Papers Tell Of '53.” The New York Times. The New York Times, June 8, 1984. <https://www.nytimes.com/1984/06/08/world/us-papers-tell-of-53-policy-to-use-a-bomb-in-korea.html>.

^v Sanger, David E. “US. General Considered” The New York Times. The New York Times, October 6, 2018. <https://www.nytimes.com/2018/10/06/world/asia/vietnam-war-nuclear-weapons.html>.

^{vi} Savage, Charlie. “Risk of Nuclear War ” The New York Times. The New York Times, May 22, 2021. <https://www.nytimes.com/2021/05/22/us/politics/nuclear-war-risk-1958-us-china.html>.

^{vii} Diplomat, Gregory Kulacki for The. “Would China Use Nuclear Weapons First in a War with the United States?” – The Diplomat. for The Diplomat, April 27, 2020. <https://thediplomat.com/2020/04/would-china-use-nuclear-weapons-first-in-a-war-with-the-united-states/>.

^{viii} Desai, Kartik Bommakanti and Suyash. “China's Nuclear Ambiguity and Its Implications for India.” ORF, April 21, 2021. <https://www.orfonline.org/research/chinas-nuclear-ambiguity-and-its-implications-for-india/>.

^{ix} Times, Global. “China Urged to Increase Sea-Based Nuclear Deterrent AMID Us Intensified Strategic Threat.” Global Times, 2021. <https://www.globaltimes.cn/page/202105/1224773.shtml>.

^x Vajpayee, Atal Bihari. “INDIA NUCLEAR TESTS, 11& 13 MAY Statements by India.” Statements by India, 1997. <http://www.acronym.org.uk/old/archive/spind.htm>.

Staff, ET “Nehru's Refusal of Kennedy” The Economic Times, 2018. <https://economictimes.indiatimes.com/news/defence/nehru-refusal-of-kennedys-offer-of-nuclear-detonation-kept-india-out-of-the-nsg/articleshow/52732667.cms.p>

^{xii} Staff, PMO. “Prime Minister's Office.” PIB press releases, 1997. <https://archive.pib.gov.in/archive/releases98/lyr2003/rjan2003/04012003/r040120033.html>.

^{xiii} Lodhi, M. (2013). *We'll eat grass but build the bomb*. The Sunday Guardian. <http://www.sunday-guardian.com/analysis/well-eat-grass-but-build-the-bomb>.

^{xiv} Staff, NYTimes. “Chronology: A.Q. Khan.” The New York Times. The New York Times, April 16, 2006. <https://www.nytimes.com/2006/04/16/world/asia/chronology-aq-khan.html>.

^{xv} Staff, ACT Turning a Blind Eye Again? The Khan Network's Arms Control Association, 2005. <https://www.armscontrol.org/act/2005-03/features/turning-blind-eye-again-khan-networks-history-lessons-us-policy#notes15>.

^{xvi} Today, Headlines. “China Tested a Pak N-Bomb In 1990'.” India Today, September 23, 2009. <https://www.indiatoday.in/latest-headlines/story/-china-tested-a-pak-n-bomb-in-1990-57105-2009-09-23>.

^{xvii} Narang, V. (2015). *South Asia Under the Shadow of nuclear weapons*. MIT. https://ocw.mit.edu/resources/res-8-004-reducing-the-danger-of-nuclear-weapons-and-proliferation-january-iap-2015/lecture-slides/MITRES_8-004IAP15_Narang.pdf.

^{xviii} Squassoni, Sharon. “Weapons of Mass Destruction: Trade Between North Korea and Pakistan.” CRS Report for Congress, 2006. <https://fas.org/sgp/crs/nuke/RL31900.pdf>.

^{xix} Staff, NTI. “Joint Declaration of South and North Korea on the Denuclearization of the Korean Peninsula.” Nuclear Threat Initiative - Ten Years of Building a Safer World, 1992. <https://www.nti.org/learn/treaties-and-regimes/joint-declaration-south-and-north-korea-denuclearization-korean-peninsula/>.

^{xx} Initiative, N. T. (2021). Country profiles. Nuclear Threat Initiative – Ten Years of Building a Safer World. <https://www.nti.org/learn/countries/>

^{xxi} Staff, SIPRI. “Sipri Yearbook out Now.” SIPRI, June 14, 2021. <https://www.sipri.org/media/press-release/2021/global-nuclear-arsenals-grow-states-continue-modernize-new-sipri-yearbook-out-now>.

^{xxii} Wong, Samantha. “Nuclear Power Plants by Country 2021.” Statista, May 20, 2021. <https://www.statista.com/statistics/267158/number-of-nuclear-reactors-in-operation-by-country/>.

^{xxiii} Staff, The Economic Times. “Ukraine and Britain to Hold Joint Military Drills.” The Economic Times, 2021. <https://economictimes.indiatimes.com/news/defence/ukraine-and-britain-to-hold-joint-military-drills/articleshow/81912962.cms?from=mdr>.

^{xxiv} Wires, News. “Biden Offers Ukraine 'Unwavering Support' over Russia Standoff.” France 24. France 24, April 3, 2021. <https://www.france24.com/en/europe/20210403-biden-offers-ukraine-unwavering-support-over-standoff-with-russia>.

^{xxv} Shekhovtsov, Anton. “The Self-Unfulfilling Prophecy of a 'DIALOGUE with Russia'.” The Moscow Times. The Moscow Times, August 4, 2021. <https://www.themoscowtimes.com/2021/06/10/the-self-unfulfilling-prophecy-of-a-dialogue-with-russia-2-a74177>.

^{xxvi} Šćepanović, Janko. “Good China-Russia Relations Are Here to Stay.” – The Diplomat. for The Diplomat, June 15, 2021. <https://thediplomat.com/2021/06/good-china-russia-relations-are-here-to-stay/>.

^{xxvii} Everington, Keoni. “CCP Channel Reposts Video Threatening to Nuke Japan If It DEFENDS Taiwan: TAIWAN NEWS: 2021-07-16 19:30:00.” Taiwan News. Taiwan News, July 17, 2021. <https://www.taiwannews.com.tw/en/news/4250097>.

^{xxviii} Yanagisawa, Kyoji. “Go Beyond Deterrence Dominant.” New Diplomacy Initiatives, March 2021. <https://www.nd-initiative.org/en/assets/pdf/GoBeyondDeterrenceDominant.pdf>.

^{xxxix} Times, Global. “Japan Would 'Lose BADLY' If It Defends TAIWAN SECESSIONISTS.” Global Times, 2021. <https://www.globaltimes.cn/page/202107/1228585.shtml>.

^{xxx} Staff, USIP. “China's Role in North Korea Nuclear and Peace Negotiations.” United States Institute of Peace, June 27, 2019. <https://www.usip.org/publications/2019/05/chinas-role-north-korea-nuclear-and-peace-negotiations>.

^{xxxix} Staff, DAWN. “No Excuse to Violate Pakistan Sovereignty: RUSSIA.” DAWN.COM, November 28, 2011. <https://www.dawn.com/news/676585/no-excuse-to-violate-pakistan-sovereignty-russia>.

^{xxxix} Staff, DAWN. “Russia Endorses FULL SCO Membership for Pakistan.” DAWN.COM, November 7, 2011. <https://www.dawn.com/news/671932/russia-endorses-full-sco-membership-for-pakistan>.

^{xxxix} Team, ThePrint. “Why Russia Is No Longer a Strategic Ally for India.” ThePrint, April 9, 2021. <https://theprint.in/opinion/why-russia-is-no-longer-a-strategic-ally-for-india-in-new-bipolar-world-led-by-us-and-china/636906/>.

^{xxxix} Singh, (Retd) Lt Gen Bhopinder. “India-Russia Relationship: Putin's Concerns with Quad Impact Ties.” TheQuint, July 9, 2021. <https://www.thequint.com/voices/opinion/india-russia-relationship-putins-concerns-with-quad-impact-ties>.

^{xxxix} Spiro, Amy. “Russia Fires Warning SHOTS, Drops Bombs to DETER UK Warship in Black Sea.” The Times of Israel, June 23, 2021. <https://www.timesofisrael.com/russia-fires-warning-shots-drops-bombs-to-deter-uk-warship-in-black-sea/>.

^{xxxix} Staff, SIPRI (2021). *South Asia's nuclear challenges*. SIPRI. https://www.sipri.org/sites/default/files/2021-03/2104_south_asias_nuclear_challenges_0.pdf.

^{xxxix} Waltz, Kenneth. “The Spread of Nuclear Weapons: More May Be Better: Introduction.” Taylor & Francis, 1981. <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/05679328108457394>.

^{xxxix} Staff, The Guardian. “Imran Khan Warns UN of Potential Nuclear War in Kashmir.” The Guardian. Guardian News and Media, September 26, 2019. <https://www.theguardian.com/world/2019/sep/26/imran-khan-warns-un-of-potential-nuclear-war-in-kashmir>.

^{xxxix} Staff, IDSA. India's nuclear doctrine and policy, 2009. <http://www.idsa-india.org/an-feb-1.01.htm>.

^{xli} Staff, NSA. False Warnings of Soviet Missile Attacks Put US Forces on Alert in 1979-1980 | National Security Archive, January 1, 1975. <https://nsarchive.gwu.edu/briefing-book/nuclear-vault/2020-03-16/false-warnings-soviet-missile-attacks-during-1979-80-led-alert-actions-us-strategic-forces/>.

^{xli} Staff, ACT. “Arms Control Today.” Nuclear False Warnings and the Risk of Catastrophe | Arms Control Association, 2019. <https://www.armscontrol.org/act/2019-12/focus/nuclear-false-warnings-risk-catastrophe>.

^{xlii} Staff NTI. “‘Night of MURDER’: On the Brink of Nuclear War in South Asia.” Nuclear Threat Initiative - Ten Years of Building a Safer World, November 6, 2019. <https://www.nti.org/analysis/articles/night-murder-brink-nuclear-war-south-asia/>.

^{xliii} Moore, Molly, and Kamran Khan. “Pakistan Moves Nuclear Weapons.” The Washington Post. WP Company, November 11, 2001. <https://www.washingtonpost.com/archive/politics/2001/11/11/pakistan-moves-nuclear-weapons/f1656801-497f-4ce0-94d9-9283de873584/>.

^{xliv} Risen, James. "Nuclear Experts in Pakistan May Have Links to Al Qaeda." *The New York Times*. *The New York Times*, December 9, 2001. <https://www.nytimes.com/2001/12/09/world/nation-challenged-intelligence-nuclear-experts-pakistan-may-have-links-al-qaeda.html>.

^{xlv} Staff, PTI. "40 Militant Groups Were Operating in PAKISTAN: Imran Khan." *The Week*. *The Week*, July 24, 2019. <https://www.theweek.in/news/world/2019/07/24/40-militant-groups-were-operating-in-pakistan-imran-khan.html>.

^{xlvi} Staff, *The Indian Express*. "Pervez Musharraf Says He Is Lashkar's Biggest SUPPORTER, LIKES Hafiz Saeed Too." *The Indian Express*, November 29, 2017. <https://indianexpress.com/article/pakistan/pervez-musharraf-lashkar-e-taiba-let-hafiz-saeed-india-pakistan-jamaat-ud-dawa-4959813/>.

^{xlvii} Staff, *The New York Times*. "Student Designs \$2,000 Atom Bomb." *The New York Times*. *The New York Times*, October 9, 1976. <https://www.nytimes.com/1976/10/09/archives/student-designs-2000-atom-bomb.html>.

^{xlviii} Staff, *BBC News*. "Aum SHINRIKYO: The JAPANESE Cult Behind The TOKYO Sarin Attack." *BBC News*. *BBC*, July 6, 2018. <https://www.bbc.com/news/world-asia-35975069>.

^{xlix} Ackerman, Spencer. "Qaeda: Yeah, THE Printer-Bomb Plot Was Us" *Wired*. *Conde Nast*, November 6, 2010. <https://www.wired.com/2010/11/qaeda-yeah-the-printer-bomb-plot-was-us/>.

^l Sanger, David E. "Musharraf Expands on North Korean" *The New York Times*. *The New York Times*, September 26, 2006. <https://www.nytimes.com/2006/09/26/world/asia/26musharraf.html>.

^{li} Staff, UN "Security Council Resolution 1373" *United Nations*. *United Nations*, 2001. <https://www.un.org/ruleoflaw/blog/document/security-council-resolution-1373-2001-on-threats-to-international-peace-and-security-caused-by-terrorist-acts/>.

^{lii} Staff, B. B. C. N. (2018, July 24). *N korea 'begins dismantling' rocket launch site*. *BBC News*. <https://www.bbc.com/news/world-asia-44933126>.